

Impact Factor: 5.19

ISSN: 2181-0664
DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664
www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 5, Issue 2

2024

ISSN 2181-0664

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0664

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 2

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 2

ТОШКЕНТ-2024

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№2 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2024-2>

Бош мухаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Мадазимов Мадамин Муминович
Ректор Андижанского Государственного
медицинского института, д.м.н., профессор
кафедры факультетской и госпитальной
хирургии

Тахририят раиси:
Председатель редакционной коллегии:
Chairman of the editorial Board:

Алексеев Андрей Анатольевич
Директор ожогового центра НМИЦ хирургии
им. В.Вишневского, главный комбустиолог
Министерства здравоохранения России, д.м.н.,
профессор.

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Салахиддинов Камалиддин Зухриддинович
доцент, д.м.н. кафедры факультетской и
госпитальной хирургии Андижанского
Государственного медицинского института

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Хегай Любовь Николаевна
доцент, к.м.н., начальник отдела по координации
деятельности грантов Межвузовской научно-
исследовательской лаборатории Ташкентской
медицинской академии

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Досина Маргарита Олеговна
в.н.с. ГНУ "Институт физиологии Национальной академии наук Беларуси", к.б.н., председатель Совета
молодых ученых Отделения медицинских наук НАН Беларуси

ТАХРИРИЙ МАСЛАХАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ | EDITORIAL BOARD

Хужамбердиев Мамазоир Ахмедович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной терапии
Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Привалова Ирина Леонидовна
д.б.н., профессор кафедры нормальной физиологии
Курского государственного медицинского университета,
заведующая лабораторией физиологии висцеральных систем
НИИ физиологии (Курск)

Гаврилова Елена Анатольевна
д.м.н., профессор, заведующая кафедрой лечебной
физикультуры и спортивной медицины Северо-западного
государственного медицинского университета им. И.И.
Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Чурганов Олег Анатольевич
д.п.н., профессор кафедры ЛФК и спортивной медицины
Северо-Западного государственного
медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-
Петербург)

Салахиддинов Зухриддин Салахиддинович
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедры ВОП №1,
Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Рябчиков Денис Анатольевич
д.м.н., в.н.с. онкологического отделения хирургических
методов лечения ФГБУ "НМИЦ
онкологии им. Н.Н. Блохина" Минздрава России

Гулямов Суръат Саидвалиевич
д.м.н., профессор кафедры оториноларингологии, детской
оториноларингологии, стоматологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Тереза Магалхайз
профессор, заведующая кафедрой Судебной медицины
государственного университета Порту (Португалия)

Юлдашев Илхом Рузиевич
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой Аллергологии,
иммунологии, микробиологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Хамраев Абдурашид Журакулович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной детской хирургии,
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Эрматов Низом Жумакулович

д.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой гигиены детей и подростков и гигиены питания Ташкентской медицинской академии

Рузиев Шерзод Ибодуллович

д.м.н., доцент кафедры судебной медицины и медицинского права Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Якубова Олгиной Абдуганиевна

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии, неонатологии факультета повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Бабич Светлана Михайловна

доцент, заведующая кафедрой социальной гигиены Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Сабирова Рихси Абдукадировна

д.м.н., профессор кафедры медицинской и биологической химии Ташкентской медицинской академии

Цеомашко Наталья Евгеньевна

д.б.н, с.н.с., заведующая отделом медико-генетических исследований МНИЛ Ташкентской медицинской академии

Хамраева Лола Салимовна

доцент, к.м.н. кафедры офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманходжаева Адиба Амирсаидовна

доцент, к.м.н., заведующая кафедрой Народной медицины, реабилитологии и физической культуры Ташкентской медицинской академии

Тухтаева Нигора Хасановна

DSc, доцент кафедры пропедевтики внутренних болезней № 2, Ташкентской медицинской академии.

Шарипова Фарида Камильевна

к.м.н., доцент кафедры психиатрии, наркологии и детской психиатрии, медицинской психологии, психотерапии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Бузруков Батир Тулкунович

д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Туйчиев Галибжан Урмонжонович

к.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой детской хирургии, детской анестезиологии-реаниматологии с курсом офтальмологии и стоматологии факультета усовершенствования и переподготовки врачей АГМИ

Маматхужаева Гулнора Нажмитдиновна

доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Офтальмологии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Каримова Зиёда Кушбаевна

доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Аллергологии, клинической иммунологии, микробиологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Саидходжаева Саида Набиевна

доцент, Phd кафедры неврологии, детской неврологии и медицинской генетики Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Зуфарова Зухра Хабибуллаевна

доцент, к.ф.н. кафедры промышленной технологии лекарственных средств Ташкентского фармацевтического института

Алимова Дурдона Дильмуратовна

PhD кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, детской стоматологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманова Шоира Равшанбековна

Тошкент давлат стоматология институти госпитал терапевтик стоматология кафедраси доценти

Расулова Нодира Алишеровна

доцент кафедры педиатрии и общей практики ФПДО Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Mamarizaev Ibrokhim Komilzhonovich FEATURES OF THE COURSE, MORPHO-FUNCTIONAL AND CLINICAL-INSTRUMENTAL INDICATORS OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA WITH MYOCARDITIS IN CHILDREN.....	6
2. Djuraev Djafar Davronovich, Abdukadirova Shakhnoza Bahronovna, Mamarizaev Ibrokhim Komilzhonovich HISTORICAL, CLINICAL, LABORATORY AND INSTRUMENTAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HEMORRHAGIC DISEASE OF NEWBORNS.....	11
3. Murotov Nurshod Farhodovich PRO- INFLAMMATORY AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY CYTOKINES IN THE BLOOD SERUM OF PREGNANT AND LACTATING WOMEN.....	16
4. Yakubova Oltinoy Abduganievna, Isakova Dilnoza Bakhtiyarovna, Suleymanova Nasiba Adashevna CUTTING-EDGE ADVANCEMENTS IN EARLY DETECTION, PREVENTION, AND PROGNOSTICATION OF PRECANCEROUS AND CANCEROUS CONDITIONS OF THE CERVIX.....	21
5. Mambetniyazov Keunimjay Sarsenbaevich, Jaloliddinov Odiljon Kozimjon ugli ANALYSIS OF TREATMENT ADHERENCE IN PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA.....	26
6. Murotov Nurshod Farhodovich PRO- INFLAMMATORY AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY CYTOKINES IN THE BLOOD SERUM OF PREGNANT AND LACTATING WOMEN.....	32
7. Salakhiddinov Kamoliddin Zukhriddinovich, Akhmadbekova Iroda Anvarbek qizi GENERAL CLASSIFICATION OF DISEASES OF THE GALLBLADDER AND CHILDREN'S TRACT.....	37
8. Yunusova Zarnigor Maksadovna, Xudoyarova Dildora Rakhimovna, Shodikulova Gulandon Zikriyaevna PREGNANCY COURSE AND OUTCOMES IN WOMEN WITH UNDIFFERENTIATED CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA.....	45
9. Mambetniyazov Keunimjay Sarsenbaevich, Jaloliddinov Odiljon Kozimjon ugli ANALYSIS OF TREATMENT ADHERENCE IN PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA.....	51
10. G.B. Mustaeva, O.S. Tirkashev, F.E. Matyakubova, N.T.Rabbimova CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INFECTIOUS MONONUCLEOSIS IN CHILDREN.....	57

ISSN: 2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

¹Mambetniyazov Keunimjay Sarsenbaevich²Jaloliddinov Odiljon Kozimjon ugli

¹Assistant at the Department of Allergology, Clinical Immunology and Nursing, Tashkent Medical Academy. Doctor of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of phthiology and pulmonology named after Sh.A. Alimova, Mrs. Tashkent.

²Student of medical biology faculty of Tashkent Medical Academy. Tashkent.

ANALYSIS OF TREATMENT ADHERENCE IN PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11397138>

ANNOTATION

In this article, an analysis is conducted on the treatment and treatment regimen of patients with bronchial asthma, utilizing scientific sources. The analysis examines the factors that prevent patients from adhering to the treatment and regimen, as well as the reasons for their poor adherence. The results of such analyses have been generalized in various countries around the world.

Key words: Bronchial asthma, doctor's recommendation, adherence to therapy, ICS, questionnaires, surveys and interviews, correct use of inhalers

¹Mambetniyazov Keunimjay Sarsenbayevich²Jaloliddinov Odiljon Kozimjon ugli

¹Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi allergologiya, klinik immunologiya va hamshiralik ishi kafedrasida assistenti. Sh.A. Alimov nomidagi Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan ftiziatriya va pulmonologiya ilmiy-amaliy tibbiyot markazi shifokori. Toshkent.

²Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi tibbiy biologiya fakulteti talabasi. Toshkent.

BRONXIAL ASTMA BILAN KASALLANGAN BEMORLARNING TERAPIYAGA RIOYA QILISHI TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Bu maqolada ilmiy manbalardan foydalanilgan holda bronxial astma kasalligi bilan kasallangan bemorlarning davolashga rioya qilishi va davolash rejimiga rioya qilmasligi yoki past rioya qilishiga olib kelgan sabalar tahlil qilinadi. Dunyoning har hil davlatlarida bu mavzudagi tahlil qilinib natijalar umumiyashtirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bronxial astma, shifokor tavsiyasi, terapiyaga rioya qilish, IGKS, so'rovnomalar, anketa va intervyular, ingaliyatorlardan tug'ri foydalanish

¹Мамбетниязов Кеунимжай Сарсенбаевич²Жалолитдинов Одилжон Козимжон угли

¹Ассистент кафедры аллергологии, клинической иммунологии и сестринского дела Ташкентской медицинской академии. Врач Республиканского специализированного научно-практического медицинского центра фтизиатрии и

пульмонологии им. Ш.А. Алимова, Ташкент.
²Студент факультета медицинской биологии
Ташкентской медицинской академии. Ташкент.

АНАЛИЗ ПРИВЕРЖЕННОСТИ ТЕРАПИИ БОЛЬНЫХ БРОНХИАЛЬНОЙ АСТМОЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье с использованием научных источников проанализированы приверженность к лечению и несоблюдение или низкая приверженность у больных бронхиальной астмой. В различных странах мира обобщены результаты анализа по этой теме.

Ключевые слова: Бронхиальная астма, рекомендации врача, приверженность терапии, ИГКС, анкеты, анкеты и интервью, правильное применение ингаляторов.

INTRODUCTION

Bronchial asthma (BA) is a heterogeneous disease characterized by episodic airflow obstruction, wheezing, coughing, and chest tightness with variable timing and intensity. Most BA patients respond well to conventional therapy and achieve disease control. However, a significant portion of patients (20-30%) have challenging AD phenotypes (severe atopic BA, BA with exacerbations, cough variant BA, early-onset BA, BA with persistent bronchial obstruction) and may require alternative therapies. These patients often experience frequent exacerbations and require frequent medical visits [1].

Bronchial asthma (BA) remains a global public health issue, affecting not only all age groups but also being characterized by its increasing prevalence in under-resourced countries. BA not only imposes significant financial burden for the treatment and management of patients but also contributes to increased morbidity and mortality, particularly among young individuals [4; 27; 28; 29; 30; 31].

Bronchial asthma (BA) causes distress to approximately 358 million people worldwide. Despite various reports on the prevalence of asthma in different populations, the lack of a precise and universally accepted definition of asthma hampers reliable assessment of asthma prevalence across different regions of the world. Additionally, relying on standardized methods for evaluating asthma symptoms, the global prevalence of asthma ranges from 1% to 22% of the population in various countries (2). According to estimates by the World Health Organization and other related sources, in 2018, there were over 300 million individuals suffering from bronchial asthma worldwide (ranging from 1% to 18% of the population in different countries). Furthermore, asthma is more common in children of school age, occurring twice as frequently as in adults (with half of the cases developing by the age of 5-10) [6; 29; 32; 33; 34; 35].

When differentiating by age, the frequency of BA in children aged 1-2 is 0.12%, from 2 to 3 years it is 0.34%, from 3 to 7 years it is 0.5%, and from 7 to 15 years it is 0.31%, indicating that the highest degree of occurrence is observed in school-age children [7; 8].

Typically, bronchodilators (beta-2-agonists, anticholinergics, and methylxanthines), leukotriene antagonists, mast cell stabilizers, corticosteroids (inhaled and systemic), and monoclonal antibodies against IgE are used for the treatment of bronchial asthma [3; 5].

Adherence to therapy refers to the degree of compliance with treatment guidelines by patients, while non-adherence leads to treatment failure. Non-adherence can involve non-acceptance of medications based on prescriptions, discontinuation of medications before the prescribed duration, or the use of alternative treatments. Moreover, therapy can be intentionally or unintentionally discontinued or interrupted. Non-adherence to therapy is one of the main challenges in providing effective medical care worldwide. It is particularly pronounced in developing countries, where non-adherence affects approximately 50% of patients enrolled in treatment programs for chronic conditions such as asthma, diabetes, and hypertension. Non-adherence to the treatment regimen for bronchial asthma arises due to the severity of the socio-economic situation, poor communication between the doctor and the patient, issues related to the use of inhalation devices, complexity of the

treatment regimen, financial constraints, self-medication, psychological factors, and prioritization of other illnesses over short-term symptom relief [10; 11; 12; 13; 36; 37; 38; 39].

One of the important challenges in this field is the low adherence of patients to treatment, which results in inadequate control of the disease and serious consequences (16-18). An important point is the choice of inhalation device, taking into account the individual's physical capabilities. Currently, in medical practice, the term "adherence to therapy" is defined by several similar definitions: "measurement of the patient's compliance with the recommended treatment"; "measurement of the patient's behavior (medication and lifestyle changes) consistent with the prescribed treatment".

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS

In a study evaluating the adherence of asthma patients to treatment and physician recommendations, conducted among the general population ($n = 32,172$) with an average age of $15.0 \pm 19.7\%$ patients, it was found that the frequency of using short-acting beta-agonists and inhaled corticosteroids was low [15].

A.C. Murphy et al. confirm the adherence to inhaled corticosteroid therapy in a clinic specializing in "difficult-to-treat" asthma among 115 patients. Suboptimal adherence (taking 80% of prescribed doses) was found in 65.2% of the overall population. Furthermore, it was found that patients with adherence rates above 80% had higher forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1) and lower eosinophil percentages in sputum compared to patients with lower adherence rates [21].

The results of N.M. Nenasheva's research showed that the single mode of using IGKS was accompanied by a 20% increase in compliance, regardless of age, gender, race and weight of patients. Over the course of the study, 107 patients changed ICS regimens, including 62 patients who switched from single ICS to double or more, and adherence decreased from 63.7% to 47.8%, while 44 patients underwent secondary and single ICS. greater use and adherence to single-dose NSAIDs increased from 8.1 to 74.4%. [14]

In the examination of Tejus outpatient conditions by Sharmila Sinha, the majority of patients supported the therapy. Only 11 patients did not respond to the requirements, of whom 7 were male (accounting for 11.92% of all male participants in the study) and 4 were female (accounting for 10.52% of all female participants). The differences in adherence rates between males and females were similar. The main reasons for non-adherence to the recommended therapy, according to surveys and interviews, were forgetfulness and difficulties in correctly using medications, particularly inhalers [9].

Apriori, researchers defined "good" adherence as using prescribed doses $>80\%$, "fair" adherence as 60-79%, and "poor" adherence as $<60\%$. The study confirmed suboptimal adherence in children with asthma since good adherence was observed in only 42% of the population, with the rest being non-adherent. Furthermore, there were no clinical parameters that distinguished between those who adhered well to therapy and those who did not, which made it challenging to implement such behavior in clinical practice. Similar to this study, as observed in 58% of cases, all families underestimated their adherence to the prescribed treatment methods compared to objective monitoring and measurements [19].

L.K. Williams et al. consider that variability can influence the efficacy of treatment in asthma patients. In their study, the initial adherence rate was found to be 26%. Interestingly, adherence was found to be better before or after periods of exacerbation of the disease. Moreover, a higher level of adherence was associated with a lower frequency of asthma exacerbations: a 25% increase in adherence was associated with an 11% decrease in the frequency of exacerbations. Additionally, 24% of patients deviated from the optimal regimen of the main therapy [20].

Abdullah H.K. and others. According to the results of the study, 42.2% of 110 patients had high, 22.9% average, and 34.9% low level of treatment adherence. There was no association between demographics and treatment adherence in asthma patients. However, good adherence was common among asthmatics who used a twice-daily inhaler, took medication starting at 5–20 minutes, used aerosolizers and turbohalers, and used budesonide and budesonide/formoterol [22].

In the study conducted by Deepak Aggarva et al., data adherence was reported to be self-reported in 78 patients (75.7%) and objectively measured in 56 patients (72.7%). Objective monitoring of treatment adherence is considered more important than self-assessment for evaluating adherence to inhaled corticosteroids in asthma, according to Indian researchers [23].

In another study by Nor Azila Mohd Isa et al., for example, it was found that among patients with poorly controlled asthma, a majority (56%) forgot to take multiple doses or stopped treatment (39%), compared to those with well-controlled asthma (44% and 27%, respectively). Only less than 50% of patients attending a primary care clinic for asthma management in Malaysia had good control, while poor adherence to the treatment regimen was common. The researchers concluded that Malaysian patients, especially those with severe asthma, need to make more efforts to improve asthma control [24].

In the study conducted by Jian Vang et al., it was found that 32% of patients adhered well to treatment, while 68% of patients poorly adhered to their breathing therapy due to various reasons. Further analysis indicated that lack of understanding of asthma management and treatment, poor self-monitoring, financial burden, fear of adverse reactions, and possible side effects were significant independent risk factors for poor adherence to inhaled corticosteroids in asthma patients [25].

In the study by Hailu Chare Koira and Tamirat Chinasho, out of the 106 participants, 62 (59%) were males, and the majority of respondents (36%) fell in the age range of 36-45 years. Non-adherence to treatment was identified in 139 (59%) patients with asthma. The most common factors influencing treatment non-adherence were forgetting to take medications (23.5%) and being engaged in other activities (17%). The main reasons for missing doses were forgetfulness, lack of clear information about the medication, and being occupied with other activities [26].

Strelova D.A. and Poletaeva N.B. conducted a study analyzing the results of a women's questionnaire, where the indicator of "adherence to drug therapy" was found to be 66.6% (51.0; 78.3), which corresponded to the average compliance rate. However, the group of men showed a lower adherence rate of 39.6% (35.5; 48.5) ($p < 0.001$), indicating a significant difference [40].

In the study by Leonteva N.M. et al., it was observed that 92% of young patients with severe asthma had poor adherence to treatment. This suggests that issues related to the development of new therapeutic approaches may contribute to better adherence among patients, which remains a relevant topic in current research [41].

According to the information provided by E.A. Sobko et al., out of the 24 patients who were fully adherent ($60 \pm 7.7\%$), 11 individuals had partial adherence ($27.5 \pm 7.1\%$), and 5 patients had non-adherence, accounting for $12.5 \pm 5.2\%$. No correlation was found between adherence and healthcare provider module, as all 40 patients scored 4 points (100%). Partial adherence was predominantly attributed to forgetfulness in using their inhalers (4 individuals, $36.4 \pm 14.1\%$), voluntarily discontinuing inhaler use despite perceiving its benefits (5 individuals, $45.5 \pm 15.0\%$), and fear of adverse effects (2 individuals, $18.2 \pm 11.6\%$) [42].

CONCLUSION: According to the findings of the study, the average adherence to the treatment prescribed by healthcare professionals in patients with bronchial asthma was 41.33%. The main reasons identified for non-adherence to the prescribed therapy were forgetfulness, lack of sufficient knowledge about medications, being occupied with other tasks, financial burden, fear of adverse effects, patient's negligence, and difficulties in correctly using inhalers that are administered through the respiratory route.

List of references:

1. Global Strategy for Asthma Management and Prevention/ Revised 2017 // www.ginasthma.com
2. Globalnaya Initsiativa po Bronxialnoy Astme (GINA) 2020 Online Appendix/elektronnoy resurs/url: <https://ginasthma.org>
3. Kim X. Mazza Dj. Astma: Allergy Asthma Clin Immunol 2011; 7 prilozhenie 1 S2
4. Globalnaya Initsiativa po Bronxialnoy Astme (GINA) 2019

5. So JY, Marmar AJ, Shenoy K. Diagnostika i lechenie. Eue Med J 2018. 3 111-21
6. Avdeev S.N., Nenasheva N.M., Judenkov K.V., Petrakovskaya V.A., Izyumova G.V. Rasprostranennost, zaboлеваemost, fenotipi i drugie xarakteristiki tyajeloy bronxialnoy astmi v Rossiyskoy Federatsii. Pulmonologiya. 2018; 28(3): 341-358.
7. Fedorov I.A., Ribakova O.G, Stepanov O.G., Diagnostika bronxialnoy astmu detey, perenesshiz epizodi ostogo obstruktivnogo bronxita v doshkolnom vozraste, po rezul'tatam desyatiletneгo nablyudeniya//Chelovek. Sport. Meditsina – 2017. – T. 17, №1. – S28-35.
8. Huang j., Huang D.M., Xiao X.X Epidemiological survey of asthma among children aged 0-14 years in 2010 in urban Zhongshan, China // Zhongguo Dang Dai er Ke Za Zhi. – 2015. – Vol. 17, №2 – P. 149-154
9. SHarmila Sinxa, A Tedju «Soblyudenie rejima terapii u vzroslix patsientov s bronxialnoy astmoy. 2019-g S 59-62
10. Djimmi B., Xose Dj. Priverjennost patsienta lecheniyu: meri v povsednevnoy praktike. Oman Med J 2011; 26: 155-9
11. Instrument vremenno priverjennosti k lecheniyu: uluchenie rezul'tatov dlya zdorovya. Amerikanskiy kolledj profilakticheskiy meditsini. Dostupno po adresu: http://www.acpm.org/MedAdherTT_ClinRef.
12. Priverjennost k dolgosrochnim metodom lecheniya: dokazatelstva dlya deystviy (PDF) Jeneva: Vsemirnaya organizatsiya zdravooxraneniya; 2003g
13. Dostupno po adresu: http://www.who.int/cht/knowledge/publications/adherence_full_report.pdf.
14. Kishan Dj., Garg K. Vliyanie sanitarnogo prosvesheniya na kompleantnost pri astme. J Indian Med Assos 2012; 110: 700. 702-5
15. N.M.Nenasheva Priverjennost lecheniyu bolnix bronxialnoy astmoy I vozmojnie strategii ee povisheniya. // Prakticheskaya pulmonologiya. – 2014. - №4 – S 2-9
16. Makhinova T. et al. // J. Manag. Care Spec. Pharm. 2015. V. 21. P.1124.
17. Globalnaya strategiya lecheniya I profilaktiki bronxialnoy astmi (peresmotr 2014 g.) / Per. s angl. Pod red. A.S. Belevskogo. –M.: Rossiyskoe respiratnoe obshestvo;
18. Burlachuk V.T., Olishева I.A. Budnevskiy A.V. Sovremennie vozmojnosti povisheniya urovnya kontrolya i kachestva jizni bolnix bronxialnoy astmoy // Prikladnie informatsionnie aspekti meditsini. 0 2013. – T. 16. №2 – S 31-36.
19. Budnevskiy A.V Optimizatsiya lecheniya bronxialnoy astmoy: rol kompyuternogo registra // Molodejnyy innovatsionnyy vestnik. – 2012. – T. 1. - №1 – S -. 48-50.
20. Vanessa M. Makdonald, Djanel York Priverjennost lecheniyu pri tyajeloy astme: vremiya ispravit. Evropeyskiy respiratorniy jurnal 2017 50
21. Williams L.K. et al. // Allergy clin. Immunol. 2011. V. 128. №6 P. 1185.
22. Murphy A.C. et al. // Torax. 2012. V. 67. № 8.P. 751
23. Abdulla X. K.Ali, Esraa Amin, Kamal Atta I Xaled Fauzi Alxayat. Faktori, svyazannie s lekarstvennimi preparatami, vlyayushie na priverjennost lecheniyu u patsientov s egipetskoy astmoy Egipetskiy jurnal bronxologii obyom 14, Nomer statii: 35 (2020)
24. Deepak Aggarwal, Manisha Bhardwaj, Bhavneet Singh, AK Janmeja Faktori, opredelyayushie priverjennost. Ingalyatsionnie kortikosteroidi v bronxax. Bolnie astmoy, poluchayushie tretichnuyu pomosh. BБolnitsa v Indii. Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research. 2017 Dec, Vol-11(12): OC14-OC18
25. Nor Azila Moxd Isa, Chang Li Cheng, Nazrila Xayrizan Nasir, Viknesh Naydu, Vishal Radja Gopal. Kontrol astmi i soblyudenie rejima lecheniya astmi v pervichnaya medico-sanitarnaya pomosh: rezul'tati perspektivnix, mnogotsentrovix, neinterventsionnaya nablyudatel'naya kogorta ASCOPE uchitsya v Malayzii. Med J Malaysia Vol 75 No 4 July 2020
26. Thzyan Van, Tsuy Chjay, Tsintin Van, Venxua Shi, Vey Fen, Sin Yan, Tsyantsyan Chan, Sinmin Se, Shaotszyun Li, Mansyan Li, «Determinanti priverjennosti terapii IGKS u bolnix astmoy» Amerikanskiy jurnal upravlyaemoy pomoshi, fevral 2021 g. , tom 27 , vipusk 2

27. Xaylu Chare Koyra i Tamirat Chinasho «Priverjennost k lecheniyu i faktori, vlyayushie na vzroslix patsientov s astmoy v xristianskoy bolnitse obshego prifilya Soddo, Yujnaya Efiopya: Perekrestnoe issledovanie» Int J Respir Pulm Med 2019, 6:121
28. Globalnie otsenki sostoyaniya zdorovya 2016 g.: Bremya bolezney po prichinam, vozrastu, polu, stranam i regionam, 2000-2016 gg. Jeneva, Vsemirnaya organizatsiya organizatsiya zdravooxraneniya; 2018.
29. Natsionalnoe sobesedovanie po voprosom zdorovya. (2018) elektronnyaya kniga Tsentri po kontrolyu i profilaktike zabolevaniy, Natsionalniy tsentr statistiki zdravooxraneniya. Dostupno po adresu: <https://ftp.cdc.gov/pum/Health Statistics/ NCHS/ NHIS/ SHS/ 2015 SHS Table A-2.pdf>
30. CDC.gov. (2018) CDC – Astma – Samie poslednie dannie ob astme (onlayn) dostupno po adresu: <https://www.cdc.gov//asthma/most.resentdata.htm>
31. Sarah Rnfaton, Asnhma deats have increased by a third a decade as hot summers, air pollution and lack of care blamed. The Telegraph. 2019 y.
32. Atsjournals.org. (2018). Tursinbek Nurmagametov, Robin Lushaxara i Paul Garbe. Ekonomicheskie bremya astmi v SShA, 2008-2013 gg. / Annali Amerikanskogo torakalnogo obshestva / Stati v presse.
33. Mohsen Yaghoubi, Amin Adibi, Abdollah Safari, J. Mark Fitz Gerald, and, for the Canadian Respiratory Research Network 2019 Nov 1; 200(9) 1102-1112
34. Freytin M.B. Geneticheskie osnovi podtverjennosti k bronxialnoy astme /pod red. A.B.Maslennikova. – Novosibirsk, 2001. – S. 130-141.
35. Cookson W.A. new gene for asthma: would you ADAM and Eve in.
36. Pulmonologiya. Natsionalnoe rukovodstvo. Kratkoe izdanie. Pod red A.G.Chuchalina – M.: GEOTAR-Media. 2014. – S 312-313.
37. Gupta D., Aggarwal A.N., Subalaximi M.V., Jindal S.K. Assessing severity of asthma: spirometric correlates with visual analogue scale (VAS). Indian J. Chest Dis Allied Sci 2000; 42:95-100.
38. Bousquet J., Knani J., Dhivert H., Richard A., Chicoye A., Ware JE Jr., Michel F.B. Quality of life in asthma. I. Internal consistency and validity of the SF-36 questionnaire // Am. J. Respir. Crit. Care Med. - 1994. - Vol. 149, © 2, Pt 1. - P. 371-375.
39. Stewart A.L., Hays R.D., Ware JE Jr. The MOS short-form general health survey. Reliability and validity in a patient population // Med. Care. - 1988. - Vol. 26, © 7. - P. 724-735.
40. Chuchalin A.G., Belevskiy A.S., Smolenov I.V., Smirnov N.A., Alekseeva Ya.G. Kachestvo jizni bolnix bronxialnoy astmoy v Rossii: rezultati mnogotsentrovogo populyatsionnogo issledovaniya.// «Pulmonologiya» 2003, №5.
41. Strelova D.A., Poletaeva N.B. Priverjennost k lecheniyu bolni[bronxialnoy astmoy molodogo vozrasta v zavisimosti ot pola. V Mejdunarodnaya (75 Vserossiyskaya) nauchno-prakticheskaya konferentsiya «Aktualnie voprosi sovremennoy meditsinskoj nauki i zdravooxraneniya». Ekaterinburg, Rossiyskaya Federatsiya
42. Leonteva N.M., Demko I.V., Sobko E.A., Ishenko O.P., Uroven kontrolya bronxialnoy astmi i priverjennost terapii u patsientov molodogo vozrasta. Originalnaya statya opublikovana na sayte RMJ «Meditsinskoe obrazovanie» №4 ot 16.09.2020 S 180-185
43. E.A.Sobko, I.V.Demko, A.Yu.Kraposhina, S.A.Egorov, O.P.Ishenko, I.A.Soloveva, N.V.Gordeeva, D.N.Okulova, N.S.Smolnikov, A.S.Deyxina, A.V.Yankova. “Kachestvo jizni i priverjennost k terapii pri bronxialnoy astme tyajelogo techeniya» Byulleten fiziologii i patologii dixaniya, Vipusk 74, 2019

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 2

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 2

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000